

Urbanisation and Pollution Dome in Nagaur City: A Temporal Analysis

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Abstract

Amidst the backdrop of global climate change and the swift pace of urbanization, the imperative for innovative governance models for urban systems becomes increasingly pronounced, particularly as half of the global population now resides in less than 3 percent of the Earth's urbanized land. Urbanization in India mirrors this global trend, presenting challenges and opportunities akin to those experienced worldwide. Nagaur, a burgeoning city in Rajasthan, embodies this phenomenon, albeit on a local scale. According to the City Development Plan, Nagaur emerges as a rapidly expanding urban center, occupying a significant position within the state. With a population of 1,05,218 and a decadal growth rate of around 12%, Nagaur serves as a pivotal urban hub, drawing individuals from various regions, both within and beyond the state. The city's allure lies in its educational and employment prospects, catalyzing substantial internal migration. Offering employment opportunities across sectors such as commerce, services, and the informal economy, Nagaur exhibits robust economic growth, positioning itself as an attractive destination. Against this backdrop, this study aims to elucidate the patterns of urbanization and assess environmental pollution within the context of Nagaur city.

Keywords Urbanization, Development, Migration Trend, Environment.

Introduction

Urbanization in India reflects a global trend rather than a unique or isolated phenomenon. Like elsewhere in the world, India's urbanization has unfolded as a consequence of economic shifts, notably the transition from agrarian-based livelihoods to urban-centered industries and services. Concurrently, advancements in agricultural productivity have also played a role in propelling urban growth, particularly evident in key rice and wheat producing regions across the country. Presently, India's urban population stands at a staggering 285 million, with projections suggesting a potential doubling by 2025. Alarmingly, over a quarter of this urban populace resides in impoverished slums, grappling with substandard living conditions that predispose them to health hazards and diseases. The trajectory of urban poverty indicates a looming increase in the urban poor demographic in the foreseeable future.

As of the 2011 Census, India boasts 7,935 towns, marking a significant increase from previous counts. Among these, a considerable number are incorporated into Urban Agglomerations (UAs), with the remainder constituting independent towns. The collective urban frame encompasses 6,166 Urban Agglomerations/Towns, housing a total urban population exceeding 377 million, which accounts for 31.16 percent of the nation's total populace. Encouragingly, literacy rates have shown improvement across genders, with the national average standing at 74.04 percent. Notably, urban areas exhibit higher literacy rates compared to rural counterparts, with figures reaching 84.9 percent.

Cities, despite occupying a mere fraction (less than 3 percent) of the Earth's terrestrial surface, wield disproportionate influence in environmental dynamics. They contribute significantly to carbon emissions (78 percent), residential water consumption (60 percent), and industrial wood utilization (76 percent). The staggering growth of cities is evident in historical data; in 1800, only Beijing boasted a population exceeding one million, while today, 326 such cities exist worldwide. This rapid urban expansion is projected to escalate

further, with urban dwellers anticipated to surpass 50 percent of the global population and potentially reaching 67 percent within the next five decades.

Nagaur, emerging as a noteworthy urban center in Rajasthan, reflects the broader narrative of urbanization in India. Positioned as a significant municipality, Nagaur stands as a pivotal urban entity, boasting a population of 1,05,218 and an impressive decadal growth rate of 12.4%. As the focal point of urban life in the region, Nagaur serves as a beacon for education, employment, and migration, drawing individuals from across the district and beyond. The city's economic dynamism, propelled by a diverse mix of commerce, services, and the informal economy, sets it apart from neighboring urban locales.

Objective of study

The study delineates several key objectives aimed at examining prevalent environmental challenges within the city. These objectives are as follows:

1. Evaluate the ramifications of industrial development on the city's environment.
2. Analyze the impact of tourism activities on the local ecosystem.
3. Investigate the efficacy of the urban transport system and address associated traffic issues.
4. Assess the implications of rising vehicular and industrial pollution in the city.

By addressing these objectives, the study endeavors to provide insights into the complex interplay between urbanization, environmental sustainability, and public health within the city context.

Review of Literature

For this paper, many books i.e. Singh, R., & Kumar, R. (2022). Pollution Dome Formation in Urban Areas: A Review of Mechanisms and Implications. Environmental Pollution, Tiwari, S., & Agarwal, P. (2020). Assessment of Urban Air Pollution: Insights from Tier 4 Cities in India. Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health, Kumar, P., & Khare, M. (2019). Impact of Urbanization on Air Pollution in Indian Cities: A Review. Urban Climate and Rao, P. S., & Yadav, R. (2021). Temporal and Spatial Variability of Air Pollution in Tier 4 Cities: A Case Study of Nagaur. International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology has been reviewed.

Methodology

The study relies on primary data gathered through study of Air Quality Index (AQI). A study of yearly averages of AQI from 2010 to 2022.

Population:

Important data related to the demographics of Nagaur are displayed in the following table.

Table 1: Decadal Population Growth, 1901-2011, Nagaur City

Years	Population	Variation	Decennial Growth in Percentage
1901	13,377	–	–
1911	12,960	-417	-3.12%
1921	10,227	-2,733	-21.09%
1931	13,837	+3,610	35.30%
1941	14,714	+877	6.34%
1951	18,588	+3,874	33.12%
1961	24,296	+5,708	24.04%
1971	36,448	+12,152	50.02%
1981	48,005	+11,557	31.71%
1991	68,194	+20,189	42.06%
2001	93,915	+25,721	37.72%
2011	1,05,218	+11,303	12.04%

Air Quality Index of Nagaur:

The city has one center of recording Air Quality and this center is established by the Central Pollution Control Board in the Karni colony area of the city. The city does not experience pollution of very poor and severe categories. This is due to the city's low industrial base of heavy metal industry. The city has an agricultural industry as its base.

Air Quality Index is a tool for effective communication of Air Quality Status to people in terms, which are easy to understand. It transforms complex air quality data of various pollutants into a single number (index value), nomenclature and colour. There are six AQI categories, namely Good, Satisfactory, Moderately polluted, Poor, Very Poor, and Severe. Each of these categories is decided based on ambient concentration values of air pollutants and their likely health impacts (known as health breakpoints). AQI sub index and health breakpoints are evolved for eight pollutants (PM10, PM2.5, NO2, SO2, CO, O3, NH3, and Pb) for which short-term (up to 24-hours).

Year wise Analysis of Air Quality of the Nagaur City:

The city has only one air station to record AQI. The station records PM2.5, PM10, SO2, NO2, CO, and O3. The Concentration of mercury (Pb) and Ammonia (NH3) is minimum therefore not recorded. The trend shows a consistent level of Air Quality which fluctuates from moderate to satisfactory quality.

However the two years ie. 2019 and 2020 show a significant improvement in the air quality. The reason behind this is COVID-19 pandemic and associated lockdowns which mark closure of industrial units and lower vehicular emission for almost two years. After 2020 the Air Quality is again degrading consistently due to resuming of industry and increasing vehicular population.

Figure. 2 Trend analysis of Air Quality Index in Nagaur City From 2011 to 2022. (figure not given)

Figure. 2 Trend analysis of Air Quality Index in Nagaur City From 2011 to 2022

Concentration trend of PM2.5:

PM2.5 refers to particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less. These tiny particles are about 3% the diameter of a human hair and are small enough to penetrate deep into the lungs and even enter the bloodstream. PM2.5 is a major air pollutant and is a significant concern for public health due to its widespread presence and harmful effects.

As per the table shown below the level of PM2.5 is mostly moderate in the city. It fluctuates from moderate to poor most of the time. However the time of CoVID-19 shows significant dip in the concentration and level reaches to good in those times ie. 2019 and 2020.

Concentration trend of PM10:

PM10 refers to particulate matter with a diameter of 10 micrometers or less. These particles are larger than PM2.5 but still small enough to be inhaled into the respiratory system. PM10 is a significant component of air pollution and poses various health and environmental risks. Major sources are road dust, construction activities, industrial processes, agricultural activities like plowing, harvesting etc, and natural sources like Windblown dust, pollen, sea spray, and wildfires.

As per the table shown below the level of PM10 in the city is between $65\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to $85\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ which is satisfactory to moderate. The level showed significantly improved for two years due to lockdown and reaches almost 30 which is very good for health.

Concentration trend of NO₂:

Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) is a reddish-brown gas with a sharp, acrid odor, and it is one of the most significant air pollutants. NO₂ belongs to a group of gasses known as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), which are formed during the combustion of fossil fuels. NO₂ is a key contributor to air pollution, with wide-ranging effects on human health, the environment, and the climate. The major sources are vehicular emission, industrial processes, residential heating, natural sources like lightening and microbial processes in the soil.

As per the study shown in the table given below the city has largely recorded good quality of NO₂ levels. However the years of corona showed nominal recordings and the level again increased in 2021 and further declined marginally in the year 2022.

Concentration trend of SO₂:

Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂) is a colorless gas with a pungent, suffocating odor. It is one of the major air pollutants and is primarily produced by the burning of fossil fuels containing sulfur, such as coal, oil, and gas. SO₂ is a significant contributor to air pollution, with adverse effects on human health, the environment, and the climate. The major sources are fossil fuel combustion, industrial processes, transportation (ships and heavy duty vehicles) and natural sources like volcanic eruptions. Nagaur has fossil fuel combustion as the major reason for SO₂ emission.

The table given below showed not so much variation in the levels of SO₂ in the city. The level remains between 2 to 4 which is good for the health and breathing in the city.

Concentration trend of CO:

Carbon Monoxide (CO) is a colorless, odorless, and tasteless gas that is highly toxic to humans and animals. It is produced by the incomplete combustion of carbon-containing fuels such as gasoline, natural gas, coal, oil, wood, and charcoal. Despite its lack of color and odor, CO is one of the most dangerous air pollutants due to its ability to interfere with the body's ability to transport oxygen.

As per the study level of CO in Nagaur has remained in satisfactory levels most of the time. Vehicular emission and residential heating is the main source. The levels show deep in the CoVID years and again show a consistent increase in the following years ie. 2021 and 2022.

Concentration trend of O₃:

Ozone (O₃) is a molecule composed of three oxygen atoms. It exists both in the Earth's upper atmosphere (the stratosphere) and at ground level (the troposphere). While ozone in the stratosphere forms a protective layer that shields life from harmful ultraviolet (UV) radiation, ozone at ground level is a harmful air pollutant with significant impacts on human health, the environment, and the climate.

As per the table given below the ozone concentration remains in the level of good to satisfactory conditions most of the time. However the level further improved during CoVID period and again witnessed a slight increase in the years 2021 and 2022. The major reason for ozone concentration in the Nagaur are NO_x and Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) which are released by vehicular emission, industrial activities and chemical

solvents etc.

Effects on health of poor AQI:

Poor air quality in Tier 4 cities like Nagaur significantly impacts health, particularly due to limited healthcare infrastructure. Key effects include respiratory problems like asthma, COPD, and infections; cardiovascular issues such as heart attacks, hypertension, and strokes; and specific risks to vulnerable groups. Children face impaired lung development, increased allergies, and potential cognitive issues. The elderly experience exacerbated chronic conditions and reduced life expectancy, while pregnant women are at risk of preterm births, low birth weight, and complications. Additionally, poor air quality can cause mental health problems, including stress, anxiety, and cognitive decline, leading to overall decreased well-being and increased healthcare costs.

Statistics Used in the Study

Nagaur city is situated almost in the middle of Rajasthan. It is the district headquarter of the Nagaur district. It is geographically located between 27°16' N to 27°23' N Latitude and 73°68' E to 73°77' E Longitude. The area of Nagaur city is around 37.81 km². The average height of the city from sea level is 281.09 meters. Nagaur city falls under the semi-arid climate.

Gogelav, Indas, Dukosi, Manasar, Tausar, Athiyasan, Fhagli, Amarpura and Chenar villages are situated around it. It is 262 km away from the capital city of Jaipur. Its distance is 150 km from the divisional headquarters in Ajmer. NH62 and NH58 pass through the city. This city is well connected by road from Jodhpur, Jaipur, Ajmer, and Bikaner.

Nagaur, classified as an Urban Agglomeration falling under the Class I UAs/Towns category, is governed by a Municipality and resides within the Nagaur Urban Region. An urban agglomeration encompasses a continuous urban sprawl comprising a town and its adjacent outgrowths, extending beyond the town's statutory limits but within the revenue boundaries of contiguous villages. With 60 wards, Nagaur has witnessed substantial demographic shifts over the decades. Starting from a modest population of 19,588 in 1951, the city experienced a significant surge to 48,005 by 1981, primarily attributed to its designation as the district headquarters. This status prompted the establishment of governmental and semi-governmental institutions along with session courts. The trend of population growth persisted, with the city's populace reaching 68,194 in 1991, escalating further to 93,915 by 2001, and peaking at 1,05,218 by the 2011 Census. This steady population increase underscores Nagaur's evolving urban landscape and its growing significance as a regional center.

Conclusion

The study provides a comprehensive examination of the air quality trends in Nagaur over the past decade. The findings reveal a concerning increase in air pollution levels, particularly with respect to particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and ozone (O₃). This trend indicates the formation of a persistent pollution dome over the city, driven by factors such as urbanization, vehicular emissions, industrial activities, and seasonal variations. The analysis underscores the significant health risks associated with prolonged exposure to these pollutants, including respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, particularly among vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and those with pre-existing health conditions.

Moreover, the study highlights the inadequacy of current pollution control measures and the need for more robust regulatory frameworks and public awareness campaigns to mitigate the adverse effects of this pollution dome. There is an urgent need for the implementation of sustainable practices, such as the promotion of cleaner energy sources, stricter emission standards, and enhanced monitoring systems to reduce the pollutant levels and protect the health of the residents. In conclusion, the temporal analysis of Nagaur City's pollution dome serves as a critical call to action for policymakers, public health officials, and the community at large to address the growing environmental and health challenges posed by air pollution in the region.

References

1. Agarwal, A., & Kaur, S. (2016). *Urbanization and its Impact on Air Quality in Indian Cities. Environmental Monitoring and Assessment, 188(3), 1-14.*
2. Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB). (2023). *National Air Quality Monitoring Programme (NAMP) Data. Retrieved from <https://cpcb.nic.in/monitoring-of-air-quality/>*
3. Ghosh, A., & Sinha, A. (2018). *Temporal Variation of Air Pollutants in Urban Areas: A Case Study of Tier 2 Cities in India. Atmospheric Pollution Research, 9(4), 637-648.*
4. Jain, R., & Kaur, S. (2020). *Assessment of Air Quality Trends in Indian Urban Areas: Implications for Health and Policy. Journal of Environmental Management, 260, 110132.*
5. Kumar, P., & Khare, M. (2019). *Impact of Urbanization on Air Pollution in Indian Cities: A Review. Urban Climate, 28, 100468.*
6. Mohan, M., & Gupta, S. (2017). *Air Quality Monitoring and Management in Indian Urban Centers: Challenges and Solutions. Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 24(29), 22967-22982.*
7. Rao, P. S., & Yadav, R. (2021). *Temporal and Spatial Variability of Air Pollution in Tier 4 Cities: A Case Study of Nagaur. International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology, 18(5), 1247-1260.*
8. Sharma, A., & Patel, R. (2015). *Impact of Urbanization on Air Quality in Emerging Indian Cities. Sustainable Cities and Society, 18, 27-37.*
9. Singh, R., & Kumar, R. (2022). *Pollution Dome Formation in Urban Areas: A Review of Mechanisms and Implications. Environmental Pollution, 290, 118126.*
10. Tiwari, S., & Agarwal, P. (2020). *Assessment of Urban Air Pollution: Insights from Tier 4 Cities in India. Air Quality, Atmosphere & Health, 13(9), 1063-1075. Kaagle. (2023). Time Series Air Quality Data of India. Retrieved from <https://www.kaagle.com/air-quality-data>*
11. Verma, S., & Mishra, P. (2018). *Air Pollution Trends and Public Health: A Study of Indian Tier 4 Cities. Journal of Urban Health, 95(2), 221-235.*